

PERSONALITY PHENOMENON IN PSYCHOLOGY

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Abstract

One of the unique aspects of human nature is its aspect related to the life of society, which is an aspect that requires the study of the problem of the individual. The study of various aspects of human existence has a long historical tradition. This multidimensionality, versatility and diversity in the aspect of a person's personality determine his uniqueness.

Keywords: Individual, cute, hot-tempered, striving, boastful, happy, sorbet, demanding, dominant, concerned, willing, excitable, restless, sharp, inoffensive.

Introduction: In the science of psychology, the issue of human nature is reflected through the concepts of individual (Latin individual means inseparable, separate breed), person, individuality (singularity). Individuals are mentally healthy (conscious) adults, babies, and mentally retarded people who do not have speech and cannot master basic skills. However, it is customary to call only the first of these as a person, because only that person can be a social being, a product of social relations, and an active participant in social development. A person who comes into the bright world as an individual will later become a person under the influence of the social environment, so this process has a socio-historical character. From early childhood, an individual is drawn into a certain system of social relations, such a style of interpersonal relations is historically formed, and he gets acquainted with this ready-made (created by his ancestors) system of social relations, behavior, and communication from a young age. The further development of a person in the social circle (family members, neighborhood residents, the public, the production team), within the social group (in the circle of people, in their hearts) is completely dependent on the characteristics of his mind and will that shape him as a person. it creates a complex of various characteristic relations that are not independent.

Materials: The same living conditions have the ability to create different forms of personal activity, as well as create different life situations. In life, it happens that if a reprimand itself arouses a spiritual feeling in someone, it does not affect the surface

of another person. Thus, the concept of a person is formed due to the enrichment of all external stimuli affecting a person with social conditions, the sum of the structure of internal educational parts (aspects, aspects, aspects, contents) of activity.

One of the most important characteristics of a person is his individuality, that is, his aloneness. Individuality means a unique combination of personal psychological characteristics of a person. The composition of individuality includes character, temperament, mental processes, situations, events, a set of dominant features, will, motivations for activity, human interest, worldview, talent, various forms of reactions, abilities, and so on. There is no person who reflects exactly the same combination of mental characteristics. For example, the loss of a loved one can be explained by the sadness of the loss of a loved one, and with it, the qualities that cannot be restored in life and are repeated in others, are the direction of the complex reality to eternity. A person, with his dignity and defects, active participation in social life, with his strong and weak aspects, created with the help of education and upbringing, is a clear, unique high breed.

Modern psychologists from distant countries (USA, England, France, Germany, Switzerland, etc.) who are representatives of the theory that the composition of a person depends on a number of factors, as a result, attribute the structure of a person to those two main factors, that is, biological and are interested in the existence of a structure that depends on the influence of social (social) realities.

There are certain criteria that characterize the achievements and happiness of each person, which require a separate field of study. This is characterized by the concept of a person who provides social activity of a person. A person is a subject of active activity, he is formed and develops at all stages of his life.

Methods: As a result of the theoretical study of the personality, the methods of its assessment were formed. These methods differ in their objectivity, reliability and accuracy. The methods, in turn, are in accordance with the theories of personality study.

Today, the main approaches to personality assessment rely on the following research methods:

Self-report or evaluation through objective materials;

- projective methods;
- clinical interview;

- behavioral assessment tools;
- Study or compare personality:
- The type and edge of the personality makes it possible to distinguish one person from another.
 - Nomothetic approach - comparative study of people in a group according to some characteristic or edge of personality.
 - Ideographic approach - studying a person without comparing them with other people.

Results: Interpretation of the person. The subject of personality psychology has a rather complicated nature in relation to its interpretation, because people are different and change depending on different situations. Therefore, it is necessary to have appropriate clarity and explanation to explain the person in understandable language. In turn, it is necessary to have a suitable language to describe the person in a suitable way. As a result, it led to the formation of unique principles of personality study and assessment tools-tests.

In understanding a person in psychology, it led to the use of a number of concepts characterizing him:

Adjectives	
№	
	Cute-hot-tempered
	Striving - boastful
	Happy - sorbet
	Demanding-dominant
	Concerned - willing
	Excitable-restless
	Sharp-inoffensive
	Whimsical-optimistic
	Self-confident - resilient
0	Seriously - loosen up
	Malicious - sensitive

1	
2	Communicator-quiet
3	Patient-tolerant-trusting
4	Free - avenger

Table 1. An example of personality assessment qualities

It is required to make a list of the above mentioned features in terms of availability and liking, and those that you need to achieve. You will be able to realistically evaluate these qualities on the example of a teacher or parent. An expanded version of this category of adjectives consists of 300 adjectives (Gough & Heilbrun, 1983). This allows for a more comprehensive assessment of the individual.

Discussion: In the long life path of a person, different categories of people have different directions of activity when choosing a life path. And this is the reason why a person's self-confidence, constant cheerfulness will end in the way he started his work. Optimism and emotional stability of a person in achieving his goal prevent him from deviating from his trust and faith. When faced with a more complicated path, Tolkien Sam Gamgee shows his distinctive and reliable model of behavior. This personality model describes a person's model of thinking, feeling, and acting (provided by Dan McAdams and Jennifer Pals (2006)), which includes a unique view of a person's nature as it is expressed in social situations and its facets.

Therefore, the next issues will be focused on theories of personality, which serve as cultural heritage of human history. Historical perspectives help to define the direction of the problems of personality psychology and serve to find solutions to the problems that need to be solved in research today.

Conclusion: Such classic approaches provide a broad perspective of human nature, which serves to conduct scientific research from the aspect of obvious personality. Modern studies studying the problem of personality are studying the problem from a personality, biological point of view. Their main criteria are also based on the interaction between man and the environment. They also study values, deviance, cultural influences, and other aspects, particularly the unconscious.

Literature:

1. Boeree C. G Personality Theories. Psychology Department Shippensburg University. 1997
2. Duane P.Schults. Theories of Personality. Wadsworth, a division of Thomson Learning, Inc. Copyright © 2005.-550 p.
3. Goziyev E.G. General psychology. T.: Teacher, 2010.
4. George Boeree.C.Personality Theories/ Sigmund Freyd. Psychology Department Shippensburg University/ Original E-Text-Site:[<http://www.ship.edu/%7Ecgboree/perscontents.html>]. P.6.
5. Kleyberg Yu.A. Psixologiya deviantnogo povedeniya: Ucheb. posobie dlya vuzov. – M., 2001.
6. www.koob.ru
7. www.psychology.ru

